

SIGNIFICANCE OF REFORMS FOR INCREASING WOMEN AND GIRLS' SOCIO-POLITICAL ACTIVITY IN IMPLEMENTATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya. *Bugungi kunda O'zbekistonda xotin-qizlarning ijtimoiy-siyosiy faolligini oshirishda amalga oshirayotgan islohotlar hamda xotin-qizlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash borasida olib borilayotgan chora-tadbirlarning muher ahamiyati orqali vazifalarni amalga oshirishda tariximiz va bugungi kunimizdagi holatini e'tiborga olgan holda o'rganish, tahlil qilish hamda kerakli taklif va tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish dolzarb ahamiyatga ega.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *xotin-qizlar, ijtimoiy-siyosiy faollik, farmonlar, Xotin-qizlar davlat qo'mitasi, zamonaviy ayol, milliy tarixiy shaxslar.*

Аннотация. *Изучить значение проводимых очень важно сегодня в Узбекистане реформ, направленных на повышение общественно-политической активности и поддержку женщин, с учетом нашей истории и современного положения в достижении этих целей. Это также важно для анализа и разработки необходимых предложений.*

Ключевые слова: *женщины, общественно-политическая деятельность, указы, Государственный комитет женщин, современная женщина, отечественные исторические деятели.*

Annotation. *An important role is played by the analysis and development of the necessary proposals and recommendations, as well as the study of the significance of the reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan today to increase the socio-political activity of women and the measures taken to support women, while also taking into account our hertory and the current situation in the implementation of the tasks set.*

Keywords: *women, social and political activity, decrees, State Committee of Women, modern woman, domestic hertorical figures.*

Introduction. If we look at our hertory, how many are great Tumaris, Bibikhanim, Nodirabegim, Uvaisiy, Zulfiya are at the beginning of the development we witness the presence of women like. They were brave, intelligent and they left their own name in hertory with their bravery. Such people the very fact that we are the successors of today is to women cause feelings of pride and honor. Our country after gaining independence, women's social and political in every field attention to their activity has increased. of women in our country increase their socio-political activity in various fields and sectors it is necessary for her to realize her abilities and opportunities creating conditions, rights and legitimate interests comprehensive support for motherhood and childhood, as well as strengthening the family institution extensive works are being carried out.

Including Uzbekistan President of the Republic of February 2, 2018 "Women in the field of support and strengthening of the family institution on measures for fundamental improvement of activity" PF-5325-Decree Number 1 was announced [1]. A number of works based on ther Decree is being implemented, including women leaders in educational institutions being conducted in the field of improving the effectiveness of the educational process works are commendable. In general, it is about strengthening the place and position of women in society in Uzbekistan important works of state importance are being carried out. After all, he imagines the development

of society without women, without their participation it won't happen. That's why women in the family, state and public affairs their safe and free functioning, their rights and interests a number of measures on the scale of our country is being developed and implemented. In particular, the year 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan On March 1, "Working with family and women, neighborhood and intellectuals measures to improve the support system on strengthening the family institution in Decree No. PF-81 and 7 of the state policy to support women priority direction, as well as the main task and activity of the committee directions were determined. On March 7, 2022 "Family and work on systematic support of women Decree No. PF-87 on acceleration measures" in 2022-2026, women's country's economic, political and to increase their activity in all aspects of their social life National program and the country of women in 2022-2026 active in all aspects of economic, political and social life to implement the National program for the development of 2022-2023 a plan of comprehensive measures aimed at was approved.[2]

From these documents, further strengthening of the family institution, increasing the socio-political activity of women, their various fields and to realize their abilities and opportunities in networks creation of conditions, unconditional observance of rights and legal interests to provide support for motherhood and childhood, to increase the influence and activity of women in society, proper promotion of work, organization, entrepreneurship, scope of work to support business ability issues of expansion have taken place.

In the decree, the society of the State Committee of Women and Girls of Uzbekistan increasing activity in life, supporting women and family radical improvement of activities in the field of strengthening the institution priority directions of the committee's activity were determined. The women's committee and its regional divisions have been updated structures were confirmed.

At her point, in Uzbekistan, there is a regulatory and legal framework in her direction to dwell on the ongoing work on the development of the base will be appropriate. Over the past years, the interests of women about 100 national and international legal acts aimed at protection the document was accepted and ratified. Republic of Uzbekistan There is what President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in her speech at the meeting dedicated to "International Women's Day" on March 8, 2018. said: "Every brave man in our country, known as Uzbekistan." First of all, a young man wants her loving mother, family, and children to be happy. of course. As our grandfather Alisher Navoi said, there is her own way he is ready to give her whole being."

The main part

Currently, there are various fields in our country women make up 45 percent of workers and employees working in industries. In particular, in the system of state and public organizations About 1,400 women are working in managerial positions. 17 of them are senators, 16 are members of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis deputy, and 1075 people are members of local councils of people's deputies is operating.

Dozens of our sisters are "Heroes of Uzbekistan", "Uzbekistan Scientist", "People's Teacher of Uzbekistan", "People's Poet of Uzbekistan", High honorary titles of our country, such as "People's Artist of Uzbekistan", received orders and medals. Out of 500 of them there are many doctors of science and academicians, thousands of candidates of science diligently serving for the development of our country with her knowledge and talent is coming Has shown activity and initiative in the life of society and the state, formation and well-being of the family with her effective work proper contribution to strengthening, motherhood and childhood protection "Reputable Woman" badge, awarded to women who joined was established.

It is known from the history of our nation that Uzbek women and Uzbek mothers are not only to the development of our country, but also the world community, the whole of humanity proud, brave and wise, famous women who made a great contribution - Tomaris, The names of Bibikhanim, Nadirabegim, and Uvaisi are not only for us, but also for us We all know that it is important for the people of the progressive world we know Also, the role of women in society, their cultural, spiritual and socio-political factors in socialization thoughts on the influence of W. Wundt, E. Durkheim, P. Jane, W. James, C. Cooley, In the works of S. Koll, E. Klapared, J. Mill, B. Shtern and other foreign scientists reflected.

O. Boriyev, M. Vahidov, L. Munavvarova, O. Musurmanova, M. Mamatov, K. Nasriddinov, M. Sangilov, U. Toshtemirov, Scientists of our country such as I. Shoymardonov, M. Kholmatova, M. Ozbekov focusing on the family, its culture, social problems, and them with a more detailed study of the social status of women in the family who based their activity on their scientific research.

The more we manage to raise the value of women, the further rise of our national pride, spirituality and culture, ensuring the stability of our families, honest and pure, selfless, patriotic, It is natural that the number of our children, who benefit the society and make our nation a showcase for the whole world, is increasing day by day. In the case. After all, he is active and smart in every way, wise, inquisitive, modern not only her family, but the whole society from a woman's work and potential it is true that he is interested. The main one who boldly carries the heavy burden of the society we are building and strengthens its foundation power is every family, every person, every citizen in our society we should not forget that women are among them.

Women in our country show their talents all conditions are created for her to work according to her abilities. There and the level of using these opportunities depends on women. If a woman sees herself not only as a woman, but also her place and status in society only if he understands, if he can direct the abilities that nature has given her not to build a family, but to the development of society with honest work if he considers it the purpose of her life to make a worthy contribution, then woman can certainly be satisfied with her life. If only the family The main goal of her life was not manifested in the end ability, unused opportunity, unachieved achievements for her to women who can achieve everything in their hearts and dreams a feeling of jealousy is formed. Then, in turn, makes her angry will lead to The good news is that in the last twenty years It is the same as being a housewife and mother of children who knows her purpose clearly along with maturity through profession in various fields of social development the number of women achieving it is increasing. For everyone in our country "Equal opportunities and equal rights are established", so getting paid, getting a job, achieving certain achievements in a certain field, whether male or female whether it is a woman, it depends on the purposeful activity of the person.

A woman's responsibility for any work is doubly strong. Where be it the education system, health care or transport sector, a woman can do her job more than anything. However, in some areas, rather, against women in appointing them to leadership positions insecurity prevails. But he is the deputy leader how many of our women, including G. Boqiyeva, B. Abdullayeva, G. Rikhsiyeva and other professors are working as active, exemplary leaders. In the 90s, professor Halima Alimova of Tashkent textile and light served as the rector of the industrial institute and then same institute Certification conducted by the test center of the Republic of Uzbekistan and took the first place with the highest accreditation score. Although it has been many years since H. Alimova moved to another job, the iron order established by them is still being observed in the institute. What for? The reason for then is that a female leader is a family to her team accepts as,

summarizing the achievements and shortcomings of the economy, chooses the easiest, most painless way to solve any problem.

Women of the 21st century are devoted to raising children and their families other values were also formed. There is their own in society the desire to find a place, the desire to make a worthy contribution to the development of society through the occupation, except for their positive situation improved household service technologies are certain made manual work easier.

The social activities of women and girls are their talents, abilities, determined by initiative. In no era are women just the boss it is not considered necessary to be or only to follow. On the contrary, the present Today, the attitude towards women has changed in a positive direction, and their mother as well as being able to use their potential abilities attention is being paid.

It is known that our country is from the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century leading enlighteners M.Behbudi, A.Fitrat and A. Avloni expressed broad opinions about the role of women in society. For example, These are the thoughts in Fitrat's work "Family or Family Management Procedures". have:

"Women's rights, of course, with religion and national values depends. Live while giving birth to girls before Islam came it is known to many that he was killed. Holy Islam religion always women orders to worship. The proverb "Paradise is under the feet of mothers" has been around for centuries has not lost her position. Islamic teachings teach women to learn, work, right of inheritance, active participation in the development of society made equal with men. In hadiths, "acquiring knowledge is for every Muslim and is characteristic of a Muslim". Family, marriage, inheritance in Islam women are given more concessions, they are not allowed to live without marriage, that's all thus the right of a woman is ensured. Dowry is one of the conditions of marriage was also introduced for the benefit of women.[3]

In the years of Uzbekistan's independence, the state paid attention to women rose to the level of politics. In the Family Code, married, family that women have equal rights with men in relationships, the family is the state protection by Until then, women many legal documents were adopted that protected the rights. Especially, employment of our women, freedom to do business significant work can be observed in terms of giving and encouraging.

The Women's State Committee is also a member of our women's society in order to increase their socio-political, material and spiritual role listen to their problems and provide them with the necessary material, also serves to find ways of spiritual support. But there are also cases when a woman becomes depressed, without knowing their rights, they are humiliated, punished and harassed by their relatives and is subjected to violence, does not have the opportunity to study, work he wanders in search, stays alone with her children and so on.

It is precisely at such times that the society does not leave a woman alone For their purpose, psychological centers for women, counseling centers, if medical, financial, and legal aid organizations are increased, they are women's If he earnestly helps to solve her problems, he is unhappy in society would have contributed to the further reduction of the number of women.

There is due to a comprehensive approach to these important issues such results are being achieved. Because not only in our country a solid legal ground, but also an effective institutional framework is available. An example of there is the activity of the Women's State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Their public organization to support their segment of the population and their effective protection of rights and legal interests became a mechanism.

Women's participation in public administration is increasingly active is taking In particular, today the members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis 17 percent, 16 percent of the deputies of the

Legislative Chamber are women consists of In addition, in recent years, the executive power indicators of women's activity in offices are 5 times higher increased, that is, from 3.4 percent to 16 percent.

The women's "wing" was formed in the political parties of the country the number of women also increased. Women's State Committee According to the data, the number of women in the Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan has increased from 35% to 38%. in the Democratic Party from 40 percent to 46 percent, in the People's Democratic Party From 41 percent to 56 percent, from 38 percent in the Social Democratic Party of Justice reached 49 percent.

Social and political rights and freedoms of 20th century women the period that served her to realize her capabilities and responsibilities it has been. Women have not seen at all for thousands of years and It was in ther century that they achieved the political rights that they had not witnessed and became the essence of their dreams. To women in ther century that attitudes have fundamentally changed and now not only family life, but the status of women and men in the life of the state and society It is noteworthy that it is also equal.[4]

The mentioned achievements are easily achieved by women no. At the same time, arranging family affairs finding time for socio-political issues, not only finding time, but fulfilling the tasks assigned to them, in the literal sense, social and political to have one's own status in matters, of which two are compared to men requires much more effort.[5]

Increasing the place and role of women in society, state management their wider involvement, political management of the country The task of further increasing their activity in the field is of great importance becoming a profession. in all countries of the world in the 21st century women are gaining equal rights in politics and in the parliament occupying significant positions. For example, 8 of the Ukrainian Parliament percent are women, ther figure is also 8 in Arab countries is a percentage. Sweden, Estonia and other European countries it is distinguished by the fact that women make up the majority in its parliaments. However, among the parliamentarians of the African country of Rwanda the number of women surpasses all of Europe in ther regard. Ther 48.8 percent of the state parliament was occupi ed by women. After that Sweden 45%, Denmark 40%7 . Ther situation itself is women's day increasingly has a modern image in political, social and economic life shows that it is becoming active.[6]

A modern woman means, first of all, she has a higher education, broad outlook, economically independent, high morale, an active leader or employee, a kind person who raises a perfect generation a mother, a respected woman, a housewife we bring before us. Such a woman is worthy of social and political of the reforms carried out in our country to ensure the status is the ultimate goal.

Conclusion

In short, the socio-political activity of women It is important to increase the reforms implemented in our country is a factor. After all, a woman is the pillar of the family and society. Our families if it is peaceful and prosperous, our society and state are also strong families will be a state built on the basis.

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